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“THE WEIGHT OF MISUNDERSTANDING: A LEADER’S LESSON IN HARMONY”

In the academe, we often teach about communication, leadership, and teamwork but sometimes, it is within our own offices that we forget to practice them. I used to believe that conflicts in the workplace always started with big issues, like unfair workloads or unclear policies. But I later realized, the most painful conflicts begin with something smaller *sumbong-sumbong*, *bagotbot*, and words whispered behind closed doors.

It started one ordinary week when I noticed that some of my faculty members were unusually quiet during meetings. They would just nod, but I could feel the tension. Later, I heard that one of them got offended because her name was dragged into a *chismis* a small story that grew bigger as it passed from one ear to another. Another teacher was hurt because someone reported something she said, but twisted in a different way. Before I knew it, friendship had turned into distance. Smiles became forced. The room that once echoed with laughter now carried an air of silence and judgment.

As the head of the program, I was in the middle of it. People would come to me privately, telling their side of the story. “Sir, ako man lagi giingon,” one would say. Another would add, “Sir, abi nako wala ko nila ganahi.” I listened, but deep inside, I felt the heaviness of misunderstanding. Sometimes, I wanted to tell them, if only we could talk openly without pride or fear, we wouldn’t reach this point.

There were also moments when anger almost took over. Some of my colleagues had short tempers easily offended when they heard their names mentioned, even if the intention wasn’t bad. I could not blame them; words can hurt, especially when one feels disrespected. But I also knew that anger can destroy relationships faster than truth can repair them. As a leader, I had to be patient. I had to breathe and choose peace over reaction.

I remember one afternoon when I gathered enough courage to talk to everyone. My heart was beating fast, but I knew it had to be done. I said, “We are all educators here, and yet we sometimes forget to educate our hearts.” There was silence at first. No one wanted to speak. Then, one voice finally said softly, “Sir, nasuko lang gyud ko kay abi nako, gi-istoryahan ko nila.” That simple honesty broke the ice. Others started sharing their side the hurt, the confusion, the things left unsaid.

Listening to them, I realized that what people need most is not correction, but understanding. Sometimes, bagotbot is not a sign of disrespect, but a cry for attention a sign that someone is hurting but afraid to speak directly. I learned that sumbong-sumbong is not always about malice; sometimes, it is a way of asking for help, a plea to be noticed.

After that honest talk, things slowly changed. We agreed that if there are issues, we would talk about them face-to-face. No more whispering, no more assuming. I started encouraging open communication istorya lang ta diretso, kay di man ta kontra. It was not easy, but over time, the tension faded. Laughter came back to the office. The same people who once avoided each other started sharing stories and jokes again.

That experience taught me that leadership is not just about managing tasks it's about managing emotions, including my own. It's about knowing when to speak, when to listen, and when to let silence heal. I also learned that as leaders, we cannot stop people from feeling hurt, but we can guide them toward understanding.

Now, whenever small misunderstandings happen, I remind my team: dili ta mag sumbong-sumbong, istorya ta ug tarong. We are all humans, prone to mistakes and feelings. But as educators, we must be the first to show humility and respect.

In the end, harmony is not the absence of conflict it is the courage to face it with grace. I may not always have the right answers, but I have learned that the best solution often begins with a calm heart and an open ear.

Today, when I look at my team, I see people who have grown together not because we never fought, but because we chose to forgive and understand. And for me, that is the true meaning of leadership: to guide not just the mind, but the heart.

